

Assessment of Human Relations Skills on Job Performance among Colleges of Education Secretaries in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed human relations skills on job performance among Colleges of Education Secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State. A researcher-constructed questionnaire was used in obtaining information for the study, with a reliability coefficient of 0.72. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. Two research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. The population of the study comprised 80 secretaries in the public and private Colleges of Education in Ilorin metropolis, and census sampling technique was employed to sample all 80 secretaries. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the questions and regression analysis to test the hypothesis. Results obtained revealed a very high demonstration of human relations skills (Mean= 3.57; SD= 0.67); while secretaries' overall job performance was rated high (Mean= 3.43; SD= 0.66). There was a positive impact of human relations skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries (R= 0,076). The study concludes that human relation skills impact on job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara state. It is recommended, among others, that cultural sensitivity be integrated into the training of secretaries, to ensure human relations skills are attuned to cultural contexts in which secretaries operate.

Keywords: Human Relation Skills, Secretaries, Job Performance, Colleges of education,

Introduction

Organizational functions are carried out by individuals who must relate together within organizations, as well as relate with many others outside the organization, to get jobs done. Human relations/interpersonal skills are individuals' abilities that enable them to interact efficiently and effectively with others (Bryce, 2022; Mohmand, 2021; Sato, et al. 2019). According to Akhademe et al. (2022), it refers to individual skills that facilitate interaction between or among employees within or outside the organization. It includes the ability to share information with others, build strong relationships, seek feedback, recognize the accomplishment of others, listen to the views of others, create an atmosphere of trust, network with professional associates, seek counsel from others, and work well with others (Akhademe et al, 2022). They added that the skills are critical for workplace success.

Secretaries are individuals who keep records, take notes and handles general clerical work in the office. Secretaries, occupying a central position in organizational structures, are integral to the smooth functioning of day-to-day operations. According to Akpomi and Ordu's (2009) a professional secretary's ability to perform her job well depends on her knowledge, abilities, and office supplies. Their responsibilities extend beyond administrative tasks to include crucial roles in organizational efficiency and communication. As gatekeepers of information and communication channels, secretaries serve as key-persons in ensuring that the wheels of organizations turn smoothly. Recognizing this, it becomes imperative to delve into the intricacies of how human relation skills impact the job performance of secretaries.

Job performance refers to the execution of tasks committed to an individual towards accomplishment of group goals. Al-Omari & Okasheh (2017) views it as the measurement of organizational success through the assessment of employees' productivity and contributions. It refers to the measure of job results and their predefined targets (Akhademe et al. 2022), while it is defined as the worth and quantity of anticipated efforts put forth by employees to execute a specific task well (Wikipedia, 2022).

Human relation skills are mostly soft skills, which help to build and maintain healthy and balanced relationships at work, as it involves personal attributes of communication, empathy and teamwork which are essential for building positive relationships with others. This is important in workplaces for maximum productivity, as organizational members including secretaries, relate with customers or clients, suppliers and others within their environment. In the contemporary workplace, the spotlight on human relation skills has intensified, with a growing recognition of their pivotal role in organizational functioning. Others see it as a measure of how adept, skilled or proficient a person is at interacting with others (Ofojebe & Akudo, 2021).

Human relations skill, which encompasses interpersonal communication, teamwork, conflict handling, emotional intelligence, is acknowledged as key a contributor to fostering a positive work environment and optimizing operational efficiency (Robbins & Judge, 2019). The increased emphasis on human/interpersonal competencies is particularly relevant in professions where effective communication and seamless collaboration are paramount, like in Colleges of Education.

Understanding the essential distinction of human relations skills and their direct implications on secretarial roles is essential for several reasons. First, the effectiveness of communication within the organization heavily relies on the interpersonal capabilities of its secretarial staff (Trenholm & Jensen, 2012). Clear and coherent communication, is vital for disseminating information accurately and maintaining a harmonious work environment (Trenholm & Jensen, 2012). According to Tantua and Akere (2022), good workplace human relation skills refer to the ability to cooperate in a right manner with others and build strong relationships. Looking at human relations skills from the perspective of managers in hospitality industries, it involves the process of creating systems, communication channels to enable group employees' relationships as well as strong one-on-one relationships

The practice of human relations is observed to involve; speaking with others in a manner that enjoys their support and commitment, smiling at people to promote bonding, being considerate with other people's feelings, being friendly and helpful, managing emotional pressure appropriately, positively handling grievances, giving positive comments and using criticisms frugally among many other practices. It becomes more important for secretaries in colleges of education, who relate with their immediate head/boss, and with other institutional workers who may require the attention of institutional managers, as well as students and parents who come around to lay complaints and seek clarifications from time to time. This shows the sensitivity of the secretary's position in educational institutions, and any failure to properly portray the institution well, is likely to result in building a poor image for such institutions which can result in poor achievement of institutional goals.

A good secretary is indispensable at promoting efficient office administration as they ensure office activities move smoothly and in the right paths, for the accomplishment of institutional goals. According to Belbin (2012), insights into team roles underscore the significance of diverse skills within a team, emphasizing that effective collaboration requires individuals with strong human relation skills. For secretaries, who are expected to liaise with different stakeholders, cultivate relationships, and ensure seamless teamwork, these skills become paramount.

Samuel (2018) studied the effect of employee relation on employee performance and organizational performance in small organizations; Sato et (2019) researched on the effects of interpersonal skills on workers performance; while Tantua and Akere (2022) considered workplace human relations skills on job performance of employees in hotels. The present study' focus is on assessing human relation skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries.

Objectives of the Study

As organizations increasingly acknowledge the pivotal role of human relation skills in optimizing organizational performance, the need therefore arose to assess human relations skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State. This study therefore;

1. Seek to provide empirical evidence on the impact of human relations on secretaries' job performances in Colleges of Education.
2. Establish the impact of secretaries on the overall accomplishment of the objectives of Colleges of Education, through the demonstration of human relation skills. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, there has been no study conducted on the impact of human relations skills on the job performance of secretaries within colleges of education.
3. The study holds importance in helping secretaries recognize the vital role of human relations skills in fulfilling their responsibilities, and also brings to light the importance of duly acknowledging the contributions of secretaries to institutional objectives.

Research Questions

1. To what extent is human relations skills demonstrated among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis,
2. Kwara State?
3. What is the extent of job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State?

Hypothesis

1. H₀₁ There is no significant impact of human relations skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State.

Methodology

The study employed the descriptive survey design to describe and interpret observed situations in Colleges of Education. The population of study consist of all secretaries in public and private colleges of education in Ilorin metropolis during the 2022/20234 academic session. All 80 secretaries in the public and private colleges of education form the sample of the study, using the census sampling technique. A researcher-designed questionnaire tagged Human Relations Skills and Secretaries' Job Performance Questionnaire (HRSSJPQ) was used to obtain data for the study. The questionnaire was duly validated by three experts from the department of Educational Management, Kwara State University, Malet. Reliability was ensured using the Cronbach Alpha method and the result yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.72. Mean and standard deviation were used to provide answers to the research questions, and the decisions on the research questions were taken using the following mean score boundaries. The mean score of 3.50 - 4.00 was rated very high, 2.50 - 3.49 as high, 1.50 - 2.49 low, while 1.00-1.49 was considered very low. Linear regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1:

To what extent is human relations skills demonstrated among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State?

Table 1: Secretaries' demonstration of human relation skills

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Remark
1	Cordial working relationship with bosses and others	3.28	0.69	High Extent
2	Cooperate with other institutional workers.	3.66	0.70	High Extent
3	Exhibit good communication skills	3.60	0.76	High Extent
4	Properly handle conflicts	3.89	0.65	High Extent
5	Show concern about problems of workers	3.43	0.57	High
Weighted Average		3.57	0.67	High Extent

The results in Table 1 revealed that secretaries demonstrate appropriate human relations skills (mean = 3.57; SD = 0.67) as evident in the scores for all the constructs. The demonstration of human relation skills by secretaries is to a very high extent as shown in the weighted average score.

Research Question 2:

What is the extent of job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State?

Table 2: Extent of secretaries' job performance

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Remark
1	Diligently carry out responsibilities in institutions.	3.37	0.69	High Extent
2	Their work meets required standards in the institutions.	3.53	0.70	High Extent
3	Contribute to the achievement of institutional objectives.	3.55	0.76	High Extent
4	Tasks handling promotes good image of institutions.	3.23	0.65	High Extent
5	Demonstrate good knowledge of tasks in the workplace.	3.47	0.57	High Extent
Weighted Average		3.43	0.66	High Extent

The analysis in Table 2 reveals the responses indicating an overall high extent of job performance by secretaries in Colleges of Education (mean = 3.43; SD = 0.66), with items 1, 4 and 5 indicating mean scores of 3.37, 3.23 and 3.47 respectively reveals a high extent of job performance; while items 2 and 3 shows mean scores of 3.53 and 3.55 respectively, showcasing a very high extent of job performances by secretaries in the institutions. The weighted average of 3.43 reveals a generally high extent of job performance by secretaries

H₀₀₁: There is no significant impact of human relations skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State.

Table 3: Secretaries’ demonstration of human relation skills on job performance

Model	N	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F-cal.	P-value
1	80	0.076	0.006	0.003	2.395	0.023

- a. Dependent Variable: Job Performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Human Relation Skills

Table 4: Table of Coefficients

Model	Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		95% Confidence Interval		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	55.136	4.288		12.858	0.000	46.707	63.565
Human Relation	2.085	1.347	0.076	1.548	0.023	0.563	4.733

Table 3 summarizes the regression results of the impact of secretaries’ demonstration of human relation skills on their job performance in Colleges of Education. The result indicates that there was a positive impact of human relations skills demonstration on job performance ($R = 0.076$). while R Squared of 0.006 indicated that secretaries’ human relation skills explained 0.06% variations in their job performance. The test of significance in Table 4 indicates that secretaries’ demonstration of human relation skills impacts their job performance ($B = 2.085$; $t_{(79)} = 1.548$, $P=0.023$). This shows that at a 5% level of significance, there is enough evidence that the regression equation is well specified and that secretaries’ demonstration of human relation skills impacts their job performance in Colleges of Education. Based on this submission, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that secretaries’ cordial relationship in the workplace, cooperation, exhibition of good communication skills, proper handling of conflicts, and their show of concern for problems encountered by other workers and students, positively impact their performance in colleges of education.

Discussion of Findings

From the result of the study, there was evidence of a very high demonstration of human relations skills by secretaries in Colleges of Education. The secretaries ensured good communication, promoted cooperation, handled problems and institutional conflicts, and promoted collaboration among institutional members for the accomplishment of institutional objectives. This agrees with the submission of Akhademe, et al. (2022) whose result shows that human relations skills were rated high, with a mean of 79.07% among office managers. It is in tandem with Robbins and Judge's (2019) assertion that secretaries often act as intermediaries, to navigate through conflicts adeptly as they possess robust human relation skills which equips them with the tools necessary to address conflicts diplomatically, ensuring a harmonious work environment. The result is also in line with the earlier findings of Olorisade (2008) who submitted that intermediate managers in colleges of education demonstrate requisite managerial skills to a large extent, in discharging their duties.

The findings again indicate an overall high job performance by secretaries in colleges of education (mean = 3.43; SD = 0.66). This reveals secretaries who demonstrate good knowledge of their jobs, endeavor themselves to people, handle tasks with diligence, and contributing to the overall achievement of institutional goals. The high job performance of secretaries reveals individuals who successfully work with and enjoy the support of their deans, heads of departments and other staff members in executing institutional activities. This is in agreement with Akhademe, et al. (2022) submission that job performance among office managers was rated high, with a mean of 79.14%. it is also in tandem with the findings of Asher and Hindi (2014) who established the centrality of interpersonal/ human skills in organizational performance. The result again indicated that there was a positive impact of human relations skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries. This shows that the job performance of secretaries was aided by the demonstration of appropriate human relations skills in Colleges of Education. This agrees with Kanthasamy’ (2019) findings which revealed that a positive relationship exists between interpersonal/human skills and workers' performance; while Ofojebe and Akudo (2021) who reported that interpersonal/human skills significantly predicted job performance in schools. Robbins and Judge (2019) underscore that human relations skills contribute significantly to overall organizational success. Again, Belbin (2012), underscore the intrinsic connection between secretaries' human relation skills, particularly in the realm of teamwork, and their job performance. Tantua and Akere (2022) reported that workplace human relations skills improve employees' job performance; while Samuel (2018) found a weak but positive relationship between human relations and employee performance and organizational performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, which revealed that colleges of education secretaries demonstrate human relations skills to a very high extent in Ilorin metropolis, and that colleges of education secretaries' job performance are to a high extent. It was concluded that human relation skills of secretaries have positive impact on their job performance in colleges of education. It reveals the efforts of secretaries as link-persons to institutional managers, in relating with members of the institutional community and others, towards the accomplishment of the objectives of the institutions. This shows secretaries as gatekeepers of information and communication channels, who must be properly equipped to promote the good image of the institution and ensure good working relations with staff, students and other members of the public for the achievement of institutional goals and objectives.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that;

1. Secretaries should be better engaged in brainstorming sessions to solve institutional problems with other stakeholders. This will further improve their human relations skills and equip them to better handle conflicts and problem situations as it may arise, thus improving their performance further, for the overall success of their institutions.
2. Towards optimizing human relation skills among secretaries in colleges of education, navigating cultural differences within the workplace is important. This will involve integrating cultural sensitivity into training programs and organizational policies, to ensure that human relation skills are attuned to the cultural contexts in which secretaries operate. This will equip secretaries with the ability to navigate and appreciate diverse cultural backgrounds which can foster more effective communication and collaboration.
3. For enhanced job performance of college of education secretaries, they should be involved in institutional retreats organized to sharpen the focus of leaders/managers at re-strategizing and sharpening focus on institutional vision, towards attaining institutional goals. This will place secretaries in better position to effectively assist their immediate bosses in achieving institutional objectives and helping colleges of education at making greater impact in the society.
4. Institutional managers must acknowledge secretaries' demonstration of human relations skills as pivotal to success in institutions, and see secretaries as relevant and key persons for the achievement of institutional objectives. This will promote a more cordial working relationship with secretaries, and will go a long way to motivate and boost their morale, at encouraging secretaries to do more for their organizations.

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